

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Maurice****FIRST NAME: Kwizera****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 15%

The author used the following software: MS Office 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Among the following statements, indicate the one which applies to “plagiarism.”
 - When a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to its author.¹**
 - Using many examples from someone else in your academic paper.
 - Using statistical data borrowed from another source.
 - Citing multiple times, a piece of work used by someone else in research reports.
2. The following is the right meaning of the “style guide.”

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 5

A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.²

- A personal and authoritative way of packaging information to convince readers.
- A user-friendly document to inform writers on the best use of English in research.
- A particular procedure by which the students collect and document primary information in research work.

3. Identify the intruder in the following statements related to practical and conceptual problems.

Practical problems are not common in the professional world.³

- What differentiates “practical” from “conceptual” problems is the nature of their conditions and consequences.
- COVID-19 is an example of a practical problem.
- A conceptual problem does not have a tangible cost.

4. The following reasons are all valid as to why a writer needs to cite the sources of information:

Giving credit to the authors of information, reassuring readers of the accuracy of facts, and showing readers the research tradition that informs the work.⁴

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 24.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

⁴ Turabian et al., 139–40.

- Giving credit to the authors of information, reassuring readers of the accuracy of the facts, and showing the uniqueness of the work.
 - Giving credit to the authors of information, helping readers follow or extend your research, and showing the uniqueness of the work.
 - Building evidence on the understanding of the research topic, reassuring readers of the accuracy of facts, and showing readers the research tradition that informs the work.
5. Indicate the most adequate statement to qualify a “working hypothesis” in research.
- A plausible answer to the research question, no matter how tentative or speculative.⁵**
 - A final answer to the research question.
 - An answer the researcher must stick to regardless of evidence that may be found later in the analysis.
 - None of the above statements is right.
6. Choose one statement which is not a rule for writing academic papers.
- Do not use the first person singular.⁶**
 - State the main thesis and stay focused.
 - Do not make the writing boring and clumsy.
 - Indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages.

⁵ Turabian et al., 29.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14-16.

7. The following feature is characteristic of qualitative research.
- The researchers attempt to interpret phenomena and experiences in terms of the meaning people bring to them.⁷**
 - The intent of qualitative research is not to examine social situations or interactions.
 - The research participants and related experiences are not necessary to mention.
 - It is not possible to modify the research questions.
8. In chapter three of a dissertation also known as “methodology and research approach,” the reader expects various information except ...
- The situation of the study in the context of previous research.⁸**
 - The research design and the specific procedures used in conducting the study.
 - Knowledge of the current issues and discourse.
 - The theoretical basis of the data collection methods used and why they were chosen.
9. What is a research claim?
- The answer to the research question as expressed in the research argument.⁹**
 - The data collected by the researcher through primary sources.
 - The existing information when supplemented by new experiments.
 - The working hypothesis of the research.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 144-145

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 433–34.

⁹ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 59.

10. What research method is not adequately described among the following?

- The grounded theory method is aimed at generating sound information to create a new theory.¹⁰**
- A case study is a research method typically extensive and draws on multiple methods of data collection
- Ethnography is rooted in cultural anthropology and involves extended observations.
- Phenomenological research involves studying a small number of subjects through extensive and prolonged engagement to develop patterns and relationships of meaning.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 433–34.

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